

Simion Zoo : A training Workbench for Reinforcement Learning allowing Distributed Experimentation

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Abstract

Simion Zoo is a Reinforcement Learning (RL) workbench developed for training of novel users that can be deployed over computer farms allowing extensive experimentation over distributed resources. In this paper, we present this software platform and share some of the insights gained during the development. This workbench provides a complete set of tools to design, run, carry out statistical analysis of the results, report preparation, and have qualitative visual assessment of the simulation evolution of continuous RL control experiments. The main features that set apart Simion Zoo from other software packages for introduction to RL experimentation are its easy-to-use GUI, its support for distributed execution including deployment over graphics processing units (GPUs), and the possibility to explore concurrently the RL hyper-parameter space, which is key to successful RL experimentation.

Keywords:

Reinforcement Learning, Continuous space control, Training environment

1. Introduction

In recent years, Reinforcement Learning (RL) [?] has become a very popular area of research, because of the almost exponential increase in computing power due to the advent of dedicated GPUs that have empowered researchers to face previously unapproachable problems. In particular, the successful applications of Deep Reinforcement Learning (DRL) to produce master level video-game players [?] have created great expectations about the potential of DRL, inside and outside the academic research community. As a result of this popularity boost, the number of free open source RL software packages has grown significantly. Nevertheless, these projects are mostly oriented

towards the research community, i.e. they assume the user has already high level programming skills and access to powerful computing resources to run the software. Even for sophisticated programmers, these packages impose a steep learning curve that hinders their user experience. This is in stark contrast with the *de facto* user standards for conventional Machine Learning software, which customarily [?] allows users to design/run experiments, and to analyze the results using an intuitive Graphical User Interface (GUI), allowing a much more swift learning curve. Simion Zoo has been designed with the aim to provide users, regardless of their programming skills, the ability to design and run RL experiments quickly on inexpensive and commonly available hardware.

Let us enumerate the most important features of Simion Zoo as a user-friendly tool: (a) easy installation, (b) a friendly GUI usable by non-programmers, (c) graphical visualization of the experiment and relevant data structures that help to understand the performance achieved by the learning process, (d) facilities for statistical analysis of the results, (e) concurrent exploration of meta-parameter space that reduces the actual time spent in trial-and-error model exploration, (f) efficient use of heterogeneous computing resources over local area networks (LAN), and (g) building the user application with easy access to a broad range of RL problems, algorithms and controllers.

The paper is structured as follows. First, Section ?? briefly reviews other related works, Section ?? presents the Simion Zoo workbench, and Section ?? discusses the availability of the project documentation and its requirements. Finally, we discuss our conclusions on Section ??.

2. Related Work

There is a whole ecosystem of software available for RL experimentation. At the bottom layer, there are some very popular Neural Network libraries such as Tensorflow, Caffe, or CNTK. These libraries implement neural networks, that are the cornerstone upon which current DRL research is built. Keras builds upon *Tensorflow* to provide a higher-level interface to train and evaluate neural networks. These are libraries aim to provide support for generic Deep Learning tasks, and as such, do not implement any RL methods, nor any visualization or result analysis capability.

One level above in the free open source software hierarchy are RL libraries that provide algorithms and environments. Currently, some of the

most popular are Gymnasium, Stable Baselines, Open AI Baselines, Tensorflow Agents, Keras RL, or RL Lib (Ray project). These libraries provide implementations of state-of-the-art RL methods and some facilities to build up a broad set of experimental environments where agents can be trained. Although installing these software packages and running RL experiments with them is a relatively simple task for the experienced programmer, often it becomes a nearly impossible task for users with amateur level programming skills. Some of these libraries for the construction of experimental environments allow real-time visualization of the RL training experiment evolution, but the training/evaluation process and the hyper-parameters involved need to be coded down by the user. We found only one library, namely RL Lib (Ray project), that allows the user to define ranges for hyper-parameters and supports distribution of the execution of the RL experiments over a farm of computers. However, its learning curve is rather steep, touching topics that go well beyond DRL.

Close to the design of Simion Zoo, we found two RL simulation environments that offer a full GUI to edit, run and view/analyze RL experiments, namely Maja Machine Learning Framework (MMLF), and RL Sim. They implement a rather limited set of RL agents and environments, do not support any form of hardware acceleration (i.e. *GPU programming*), and do not support multi-valued hyper-parameters.

Regarding the programming language, most of these software packages are written in Python, which has become in the last years the standard for Data Science. There are a few notable exceptions written in Java (i.e., *RL Sim*), or C++ (*RL Lib*, not to be confused with the *Ray project* referred above).

The development of an RL experimentation environment, its upgrade and maintenance to keep up with the speed of new methods developed by researchers worldwide is a very demanding task. For such a project to be successful, it requires a highly motivated community of developers/contributors. Some of these projects are maintained using institutional funding, but most of them depend on the good will of a community of independent developers. The engagement of these developers oftentimes shifts to a different project. Hence, it is not uncommon to see projects that are abandoned in favor of others. Some of the projects that have been abandoned include: pyBrain, RL Park, RL Lib, RL Library, *Maja Machine Learning Framework* or *RL Sim*. In this context, Simion Zoo proposes a stable platform that is not dependent of changing software developer paradigms

3. Simion Zoo

Simion Zoo [?] is a workbench to test RL and DRL algorithms that focuses on model-free RL learning algorithms applied to control problems defined on continuous state and action spaces. It has been published as free open source in Zenodo [?], and Github (<https://github.com/simionsoft/SimionZoo> accessed January 1, 2023), with the following salient features:

- (a) Simion Zoo can be installed over a farm of heterogeneous computers communicated via LAN in a master/slaves configuration. The installation process is straight-forward. One single installer application provides the installation of the service/daemon on the slave machines (*Herd Agent* application). On the master computer, the user needs only to run the main application (named *Badger*), which requires no installation and bundles all the dependencies without user intervention.
- (b) The configuration, execution and analysis of results of the RL experiments is carried out via a user-friendly GUI on the master host computer.
- (c) Experiments can be run either locally in the master computer or distributed over other computers in the local network.
- (d) A specific tool for the analysis of finished experiments is provided. This tool generates publication-quality plots and statistics of the system variables over the training and testing of the system.
- (e) Parameters can be *forked* and given as many values as desired, so that experiments with all the parameter value combinations may be run concurrently.
- (f) Each machine used during an experiment receives binaries which are compatible with its own operating system and architecture, taking advantage of all the resources available on the computer (all the CPU cores and/or the GPU). The project currently supports *Windows* and *Linux* operating systems.
- (g) The workbench comes with a wide set of built-in environments and agents, that can be tailored by the user through the GUI without coding.

In the remainder of this section, we will review the structure and the most prominent features of the *Simion Zoo* software package.

3.1. Software Platform

The three core software components in the workbench are the following:

- **RL Simion:** a console application that runs an *experimental unit*. All the hyper-parameters used by the object classes involved in an experimental unit are configured via an input file that completely defines an instance of an *experiment*. We make an explicit distinction between *experimental units* (with single-valued hyper-parameters) and *experiments* (which may contain multi-valued hyperparameters). Several object classes can be used in an experiment, each of them with their own set of hyper-parameters. Figure ?? shows a simplified UML scheme of RL Simion. This component is written in C++.
- **Badger:** a master application endowed with a *Graphical User Interface* (GUI) that allows the user to design an experiment (*Badger Editor*), distribute the workload among the available machines and monitor the progress of the experiment in real time (*Badger Monitor*), and analyze the results after an experiment is finished (*Badger Reports*). This component is written in C#.
- **Herd Agent:** a *daemon* process that can be installed in the machines of the computer farm accessed by LAN. This process acts as a server that can receive experimental units from the *Badger*, run them while sending live monitoring information, and send the results to *Badger* once an experimental unit is finished. This component is written in C#.

3.2. Narrative description of setting up an RL experiment.

Figure ?? illustrates the interactions between these three components during the the process of conducting a RL experiment, which begins with the user designing a RL experiment in the *Badger Editor*. Figure ?? shows the *Badger* GUI providing graphic objects that allow the user to configure the experiment easily.

3.2.1. Facilities for hyper-parameter value grid search.

Experiment hyper-parameters can be of a variety of types (for example, integer/real numbers, boolean, or strings) and can be assigned multiple values using a *fork* (such as the one used on the hyper-parameter *Delta-T* on Figure ??). These multi-valued hyper-parameters allow the user to perform a *parameter sweep* so that the best combination of parameter values can be found and used. The ability to carry out parameter sweeps is very useful when conducting RL experiments, because a lot of hyper-parameters need to be configured and there is no analytical rule to set them. Thus, finding appropriate hyper-parameters usually requires tweaking and testing different values, which takes a lot of time and computational resources. Simion Zoo allows to configure this parameter exploration from the GUI with minimal effort.

3.2.2. Automated consistent definition of hyper-parameters.

While a researcher carries out exploratory experiments, it is very common to have frequent changes in the code that have impact on the parameterization of the experiment itself. For example, a researcher may want to change the definition of the architecture of a neural network. This change forces changes in the definition and values of the hyper-parameters that need to be configured. *Simion Zoo* addresses this issue by using special template classes to define hyper-parameters in the code along with associated metadata (see the code snippet in Figure ??). The *RL Simion* module launches an automated task that parses the C++ code looking for hyper-parameters defined using these object classes. This task is automatically run every time the code is built from the user graphical specification. The output of this task is a configuration file with the definitions of all the object classes and their hyper-parameters. The *Badger Editor* loads this file on start-up (a sample of a simplified configuration file is shown in Figure ??), and it dynamically creates a GUI that is automatically prompted to the user to provide the value of every hyper-parameter. Once the experiment is saved or run, it generates an XML configuration file for each experimental unit. These files are then provided as the input for an instance of RL Simion. This fully automated process ensures that the actual hyper-parameters of an experiment will always match the hyper-parameters viewed by the current version of *RL Simion*. The user is fully protected against errors in the specification of experiments that can be very tricky to solve. This process is illustrated in Figure ??.

3.2.3. Local versus distributed execution of experimental units.

Once the experiment has been configured, the user can run it locally or remotely. Local execution allows the user run a single experimental unit using the local machine. On the other hand, remote execution enables the user to distribute the workload of experimental unit runs over the machines in the local computer farm where *Herd Agent* has been installed.

Local execution is meant to help the user to grasp intuitively the behavior of the agent. For this purpose, the user is shown a real-time graphical representation of the agent interacting with the environment while the experimental unit is run. Figures ?? and ?? show two snapshots of this graphical representation on two different environments. These snapshots also include bar meters showing the current value of the state and action variables, and color-maps representing the functions being learned by the agent (policies and/or value functions).

On the other hand, remote execution takes advantage of other machines to increase the availability of computational resources. Experimental units are distributed among these other machines so that they can be run in parallel. The user can carry out this workload distribution on the *Badger Monitor*.

3.2.4. Running a distributed execution.

First, the user selects the machines to be used from those that are available. Then, the *Badger* creates a set of experimental units, one for each of the possible combinations of the multi-valued hyper-parameters in the experiment. Figure ?? shows a simplified version of a file with hyper-parameters that define an experimental unit. As specified in Figure ?? these hyper-parameters are the main input of the RL Simion module

After experiments are split into experimental units, the *requirements* of each experimental unit are automatically set. Requirements for execution include the experimental unit configuration file, any other files required for the specific environment used in the simulation (e.g., wind files if the OpenFast simulator is used), or dependencies (e.g., the CNTK library if Deep RL algorithms are used). Platform dependent requirements (e.g., the specific binaries of a dependency) cannot be completely resolved until the target machine where it will run is allocated. *Badger Monitor* distributes the experimental units among the available machines: as many to each one as it can handle in parallel, until all the available machines are busy. If a GPU can be used, each machine receives only one experimental unit, and if only the CPU can be used, one unit per CPU core.

After an experimental unit is scheduled for execution on an specific machine, the platform-dependent requirements are resolved. Several experimental units may be batched as a job that consists on one or more tasks (experimental units), and all the files needed to run each of these tasks (i.e. the executable and all the requirements) are sent to the target Herd Agent . This process is illustrated in Figure ?? . While an experiment is running, the performance of each single experimental unit is monitored from the *Badger Monitor*. This live monitoring is shown in Figure ??, and it allows early detection of a failed experiment, thus accelerating the usual try-and-error cycle involved in experimenting with RL.

3.2.5. Generation of reports.

After all the experimental units in the current experiment have finished, the result files returned by the Herd Agents can be analyzed in *Badger Reports* (see Figure ??). This control allows the user to perform a great variety of queries on the data, selecting which variables to analyze, grouping experimental units by fork, or selecting a subset of the experimental units. The results of these queries are shown both as tabular data and as time-series plots. These plots can be exported as publication-ready images, such as those in [?]. Figure ?? shows a sample plot generated with *Badger Reports*. Another interesting feature of this module is the exportation of visual representations of the functions learned by the agent. Figure ?? shows a sequence of images visualizing the evolution of a function at various times during the learning process of experiment.

3.3. Available RL algorithms and environments

Simion Zoo bundles a set of built-in features that can be used to design RL experiments without any additional coding by the end user. The set of built-in algorithms include:

- Conventional controllers: Proportional Integrative Derivative, Linear-Quadratic Regulators, and Variable-Speed Wind-Turbine (VSWT) specific controllers [?],
- RL methods: SARSA, Q-Learning [?], Double Q-Learning [?], CA-CLA [?], regular gradient ascent, Incremental Natural Actor-Critic [?], Off-Policy Actor-Critic [?], and Off-Policy Deterministic Actor-Critic [?],

Figure 1: Visual representation of software architecture used in *Simion Zoo*. First, the user designs an experiment in *Badger* setting the value of every hyper-parameter. In this example, there are two multi-valued hyper-parameters: x and y . Then, the experiment is split as a batch of experimental units, and these are distributed among the available machines. *Badger* receives live monitoring information while an experimental unit is running and, when an experimental unit finishes, the log files.

- Deep RL methods: DQN [?], Double-DQN [?], DDPG [?] and Deep CACLA [?].

Besides, when using an Actor-Critic architecture, policy learners (Actors) can be combined with different value function learners (Critics): Temporal-Difference(λ), TDC(λ), and True Online Temporal-Difference [?]. RL methods can use one of the two Linear Value Function Approximation methods included in the package: *Gaussian Radial Basis* functions and *Tile-coding*.

The package includes the following environments where agents can be trained or evaluated :

- Classical bench-marking control tasks: mountain-car, balancing pole, swing-up pendulum, and double swing-up pendulum,
- Benchmark tasks from the literature[?]: underwater vehicle control and airplane pitch control,
- Several single and multi-robot control problems supported by the *Bullet Physics* library, and

Figure 2: Snapshot of *Badger Editor*: the user can configure the hyper-parameters of the experiment. In this example, the hyper-parameter ΔT is assigned two different values using a *fork*.

Figure 3: Snapshot of *Badger Monitor*: the user can select which machines to use before launching an experiment and, during the experiment, the performance of each experimental unit is represented as a time-series line in the plot.

Figure 4: Snapshot of *Badger Reports*: the user can perform different types of queries on the data gathered after running an experiment, analyze it, and also export plots generated from the data.

Figure 5: Sample plot generated with *Badger Reports*, showing the averaged rewards of three different experimental units as a time series line.

Figure 6: Sample plot generated with *Badger Reports*, showing the averaged rewards of three different experimental units as a time series line.

Figure 7: A simplified UML diagram of the basic class hierarchy and their configurable parameters.

```

Experiment::Experiment(ConfigNode* pConfigNode)
{
    m_numTrainingEpisodes = INT(pConfigNode, "Num-Episodes"
        , "Number of training episodes", 1000);
    m_progUpdateFreq = DOUBLE(pConfigNode, "Progress-Update-Freq"
        , "Progress update frequency (seconds)", 1.0);
    m_episodeLength = DOUBLE(pConfigNode, "Episode-Length"
        , "Length of an episode (seconds)", 10.0);
}
  
```

Figure 8: Code snippet from the construction method of an *Experiment* class object. *DOUBLE* and *INT* are classes that include meta-data and initialize hyper-parameters in a uniform manner.

```

<DEFINITIONS>
  <CLASS Name="Experiment">
    <INTEGER-VALUE Name="Num-Episodes"
      Comment="Number of training episodes" Default="1000"/>
    <DOUBLE-VALUE Name="Progress-Update-Freq"
      Comment="Progress update frequency (seconds)" Default="1.0"/>
    <DOUBLE-VALUE Name="Episode-Length"
      Comment="Length of an episode (seconds)" Default="10.0"/>
  </CLASS>
</DEFINITIONS>

```

Figure 9: Snippet from the *Badger* XML configuration file automatically generated when RL Simion is built.

```

<Experiment>
  <Num-Episodes>1000</Num-Episodes>
  <Progress-Update-Freq>0.5</Progress-Update-Freq>
  <Episode-Length>200.0</Episode-Length>
</Experiment>

```

Figure 10: Sample of a RL Simion configuration file generated with Badger from the GUI. This code initializes the parameters of the object class *Experiment*.

Figure 11: Diagram showing how the automated parsing process used after the compilation of *RL Simion* is used as input of *Badger*.

Figure 12: A screenshot of a *RL Simion* experiment on the *Airplane-pitch* environment.

Figure 13: A screenshot of a *RL Simion* experiment on the *Mountain-car* environment.

- Two VSWT models: a two-mass model, and OpenFAST, which is considered the state-of-the-art of Wind Turbine simulation.

3.4. Tutorials

The project features two different tutorials: a user guide and a developer guide. The first is intended to guide end-users that would like to run experiments using the User Interface, whereas the second aims to guide developers willing to extend its capabilities.

4. Usability experiment

4.1. Experimental setup

In order to assess the usability of this software in comparison with other solutions for RL introductory training, we conducted an experiment with a small cohort of fourth year students of the *Bachelor Degree in Computer Management and Information Systems Engineering* at the *Faculty of Engineering of Vitoria-Gasteiz (University of the Basque Country-UPV/EHU)*. Recruited students are enrolled in at least one fourth grade course, and they all have some programming skills (mostly using *Java*). We randomly selected 12 students from the 15 who volunteered for this test. We divided them in 6 groups of two students, and allow them one hour to complete as many as possible of the following tasks: a) install the specified RL software package, b) train an agent on an environment (any), c) graphically visualize the experiment, and d) increment the learning rate by 1 percent and re-run the experiment. Students were provided one computer per group with no specific programming environment installed and administrator privileges so that they could install any software. These computers operating system was Windows 10 (the only one currently available in our university). They were allowed to browse the internet for help, but they were not allowed to help other teams or communicate with any of them. They were requested to notify the lecturer supervising the test as soon as they finished a task, so that the time to reach each of the milestones was noted down. We used three different software packages in this test: *Simion Zoo*, *Stable-baselines 3*, and *Tianshou*. Each of these packages was given to two of the groups as a link to the *GitHub* repository where the project is hosted.

The time required by each group to complete the proposed tasks are shown in Table ??, where '-' denotes an unfinished task. It is clear that in

this settings, the groups using *SimionZoo* fared better than the rest. The experimental cohorts are small, so we can not give a definitive assertion about the superiority of *SimionZoo*. However, the registered results give a clear demonstration that it has some advantages for teaching introductory RL concepts and providing motivation for further research with more sophisticated tools. Below are some detailed comments on the experiment realization.

SimionZoo. The two groups that were given a link to the *SimionZoo* repository (Group 1 and Group 2) were the only ones to complete all the tasks. As many of our students, these groups were familiarised with installing Windows binaries, and they were able to install the software without a problem. They then followed the tutorial available on GitHub, and were able to visualize the experiment directly as it was running. They spent some minutes trying to understand where the agent’s learning rate could be changed, but both groups were able to do it within the duration of the experiment.

Baselines 3. Group 3 and Group 4 went as far as replicating an experiment taken from the *Baselines 3* tutorial, but in both cases, the experiment crashed mid-execution due to the same execution-time error. Only Group 4 was able to solve this error (due to a missing Python package *-ipython-* that is not listed in the installation procedure) and finish the execution of the experiment. Group 4 managed to visualize the result following the tutorial (after installing another unlisted package *-moviepy*), but failed to figure out how to change the learning rate of the agent in the script.

Tianshou. Groups 5 and 6 were able to install their software using the instructions on GitHub, but none of the them was able to run the experiment in the tutorial. They were stalled by syntax errors thrown by the Python interpreter. After the experiment had ended, we followed their steps and found that there are several typos in the tutorial. We were able to solve them in a few minutes due to our more extensive programming skills, but the students were not able to move forward.

5. Conclusions

In this paper we have presented *Simion Zoo*, which is an RL experimenting workbench providing an intuitive GUI to design, run and analyze RL

Table 1: Time (in *mm:ss* format) required by each group of students to complete the tasks. The '-' character denotes unfinished tasks.

Group	Software package	Task A	Task B	Task C	Task D
1	Simion Zoo	7:10	15:50	15:50	25:05
2	Simion Zoo	5:45	12:20	12:20	38:50
3	Stable-baselines 3	21:35	-	-	-
4	Stable-baselines 3	19:00	26:25	-	-
5	Tianshou	18:50	-	-	-
6	Tianshou	8:25	-	-	-

experiments on control tasks. In contrast with most of the free open source software available in the area, this software platform allows users with no coding skills to conduct sophisticated Reinforcement Learning experiments following intuitive GUIs that protect them from inadvertent specification errors.

Simion Zoo includes installers than bundle all required dependencies, therefore relieving the user from installing dependencies and dealing with software versioning. All the hyper-parameters within an experiment can be configured in an intuitive manner from the GUI. The results of an experiment can be graphically and statistically analyzed from the GUI. Experiments can be distributed among an heterogeneous set of machines with potentially different Operative Systems and/or architectures by using hyper-parameter forking. All these features result in a swift learning curve, and it brings the user experience closer to the one offered by *Weka* for Machine Learning experiments [?]. Our research group has used Simion Zoo for some years now in our research[? ? ?].

The target users are researchers in their initial stages of experimentation with RL algorithms and the general public lacking any coding skills. While researchers are often used to write code and adapt code written by third parties, other users are not able to use any of the other RL tool-sets available. Similarly, researchers often have access to higher-end hardware that is not available for the general public. Thus, using a GUI that enables the user to design and monitor an experiment is key in order to target a broader audience. It is also very important to provide workload distribution tools, so that heterogeneous lower-end hardware can be used to run experiments with

otherwise prohibitive computational requirements.

Choosing the appropriate programming language is another very important decision that may severely affect the success of the project. We decided to use C++ to code RL Simion because: it was the programming language we were most familiar with, we expected it to produce faster code than other popular languages such as Python, Java or C#, and because C++ code is portable to potentially any existing hardware. While in our view all three reasons stand true, we have come to see during the development of this project that higher-level languages are better suited for the task. Most of the code in RL research is developed in Python and thus, cannot be used directly from our own code. Besides, while C++ is very efficient (speed-wise), developing in such a low-level programming language requires a lot more time than using a higher-level language. Lastly, most of the developers are familiar with higher-level programming languages but have little skills in lower-level programming. This hinders the engagement of the community in projects developed in lower-level languages such as this. These three arguments outweigh in the long term those in favor of using C++.

Future work will focus on the integration of more advanced and up to date computational facilities, such as existing Python agents and environments. Cutting-edge DRL algorithms for continuous action spaces, like TD3, PPO, and SAC will be made available seamlessly.

6. Data Availability

The datasets generated and/or analysed during the current study are available in the GitHub repository (<https://github.com/simionsoft/SimionZoo> accessed January 1, 2023).

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